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Research Article

ACADEMIC CHEATING AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTSAneeqa Bakhtiyar¹, Anam Ibrahim¹, Maheen Ihsan²¹ Shaheed Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto Medical University² King Edward Medical University**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Cheating in medical school may be a predictor of dishonesty in future medical practice. This has a detrimental effect on medical practice because students who cheat during medical school follow the same behavioural pattern later on in their work with patients. This study was conducted in students of Federal Medical and Dental College Islamabad. A total of 80 medical students was included in this study. The mean age of the students was 21.58±1.23 years. Mean age of the female students was 20.23±2.23 years and mean age of the male students was 22.45±2.11 years. Equal number of students i.e. 40 (50%) male students and 40 (50%) female students were included. Twenty (25%) students including 5 female students and 8 male students reported that they never cheated during their academic career. Sixty (75%) students including thirty-five female and thirty-two male students told they cheated during their examination. Twenty-six students (32.5%) of the students told that they do the cheating on a regular basis in every assignment and examination. Academic cheating is found among medical students especially in females and that policy should be made in order to rectify these issues.

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INTRODUCTION:

Honesty and integrity are important virtues of the medical profession. Cheating in medical school may be a predictor of dishonesty in future medical practice. This has a detrimental effect on medical practice because students who cheat during medical school follow the same behavioural pattern later on in their work with patients. Furthermore, dishonesty among students may result in lack of medical knowledge and in patient harm. However, many medical schools are confronted with a high level of academic dishonesty: up to 58% of students admit to cheating at least once during medical school (1, 2).

There is growing evidence that academic dishonesty is widespread in medical and health care schools worldwide. Finally, social predictors such as socioeconomic environment and educational system have been shown to have an important influence, most notably in post-communist countries in Europe. Studies have demonstrated that academic dishonesty was acceptable behaviour among medical students and that they came to medical schools ready to cheat, indicating that different familial and cultural values acquired long before medical school have had an impact on student behaviour. Academic cheating does not happen as an isolated action of an individual but is most often a collaborative practice (3, 4).

The purpose of this study is to analyze the tendency of cheating among the medical students of different medical colleges and to study the possible causes of this academic cheating. As there are few studies that looked at who are collaborators in cheating, we investigated medical students' readiness to engage others in academic dishonest behaviours. This study will help us in improving our medical education

system, enable students to become a better health professional and give confidence to the hard-working students to boost their academic activities.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study was conducted in students of Federal Medical and Dental College Islamabad. A total of 80 medical students was included in this study. The procedure and purpose of this study were explained to them and a predefined questionnaire was served. The data was entered and analyzed using SPSS Version 23.0. The qualitative variables were presented in numbers and percentages and the quantitative variables were presented in mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

The mean age of the students was 21.58 ± 1.23 years. Mean age of the female students was 20.23 ± 2.23 years and mean age of the male students was 22.45 ± 2.11 years. Equal number of students i.e. 40 (50%) male students and 40 (50%) female students were included. Twenty (25%) students including 5 female students and 8 male students reported that they never cheated during their academic career. Sixty (75%) students including thirty-five female and thirty-two male students told they cheated during their examination. Twenty-six students (32.5%) of the students told that they do the cheating on a regular basis in every assignment and examination. When asked about different reasons of cheating 78% of the students told that they do it due to lack of preparation during their assignment and examinations, 13% of the students do it due to fear of failure and bad impression on their internal assessment and 9% of the students told that they do it in order to confirm the answers and secure more marks in the examination.

DISCUSSION:

The prevalence of cheating among medical students in our study was significantly higher. Our study revealed that the majority of the participants considered copying during the examination as academic cheating (5). A study conducted by Hammoudi revealed that the main factor which leads the students to cheat during an exam was that the students think examination method was just a test of memory rather than comprehension (6). Also, the author stated that getting high grades has become the major focus of most of the students which lead them to use inappropriate resources in exams. Some other factors which can motivate the students to cheat during exams are peer pressure, academic overload, social & curricular factors, low self-esteem and educational institution management styles. Another study revealed that peer influence was the major cause of cheating during an exam. Other motivational factors stated by the author were difficulty index of exams, getting high grades, poor understanding of the topics and low value for loyalty (3, 7, 8).

CONCLUSION:

Academic cheating is found among medical students especially in females and that policy should be made in order to rectify these issues.

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